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1. Abbreviations

FCS - Fuel Cell System

CMR - Chemical Methane Reformer

ICE - Internal Combustion Engine

HD – Heavy Duty

HDFCV - Heavy-Duty Fuel Cell Vehicle

FC - Fuel Cell

PEMFC - Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell

MEA - Membrane Electrode Assembly

H₂ - Hydrogen

N₂ - Nitrogen

FCV - Fuel Cell Vehicle

UPV - Universitat Politècnica de València

RH - Relative Humidity

PID - Proportional-Integral-Derivative

SAE - Society of Automotive Engineers

ISO - International Organization for Standardization

BOP - Balance of Plant

2. Summary

This document summarizes the general characteristics of a fuel cell system (FCS) for heavy-duty applications and its integration in a testbed facility. The chosen is part of the multi-fuel system composed of a CMR and a propulsive system. Different kind of fuels, such as ammonia, natural gas, biogas, or alcohols feed the CMR and produce hydrogen that is used to generate power in an FCS or an ICE.

The objective of this deliverable is to describe the characteristics of the selected FCS, as well as the components and sensors of the testbed and give an overview of the main requirements and adaptations that are needed to integrate the system in the testing facility.

The heavy-duty fuel cell vehicle sector (HDFCV) is in constant growth, and, nowadays there exists a popular modular trend, which consists of using several small or medium-sized FCS that fulfill the power demand of the vehicle rather than a single high-power FCS. Therefore, the selected FCS is the Nuvera E-60-HD.

The details about the FCS components are also necessary to plan the sensors that need to be included in the system before starting the experimental campaign. The specifications of the FCS are also significant when planning how to integrate it into the testbed facility. The BoP (cooling system, air conditioning, gas outlets...) of the system may imply special requirements that need to be met before operating with the whole FCS. Furthermore, the acknowledgment of the FCS characteristics allows for good planning of the experimental activities that can be performed with it and helps to understand how it can be fitted into the complete powertrain and vehicle.

Summarizing, the present deliverable provides all the technical requirements and specifications needed to carry out the FCS proposed experimental campaign.

3. Fuel cell system general characteristics

3.1 Architecture

The selected FCS is the E-60-HD Fuel Cell Engine from NUVERA. This FCS has a net power output equal to 60 kW and was selected for a set of technical reasons that are detailed in section 3.3. The E-60-HD Fuel Cell Engine is composed of the anode, cathode, and coolant circuits, and its basic outline is presented in Figure 1. The cathode circuit is composed of an electric compressor used to regulate the air mass flow rate and thus the cathode stoichiometry according to the FC current density. Following the electric compressor, there is a heat exchanger fed with coolant from the main cooling circuit to lower the stack cathode inlet temperature. The pressure in this circuit is regulated by means of the pressure losses in the stack and the heat exchanger, being the cathode exhaust atmospheric.

The anode circuit is fed with high-pressure H₂ and a pressure-regulating valve maintains adequate pressure levels on the anode side to prevent the MEA from suffering mechanical damage. The anode recirculation is passive and when the concentration of other species in the anode increases over a certain threshold, part of the gas in the anode circuit is purged into the cathode exhaust stream.

The cooling circuit is composed of a coolant pump, a heater, and a thermostatic valve that is closed or open connecting the coolant with an external heat exchanger with the environment depending on the operating conditions. In this sense, the cooling circuit is used to keep the temperatures of the FC stack, the electric motor, and the cathode inlet temperature stable and under acceptable values. The FC system features a cold start system with internal heating. An important note about the cooling circuit is that it must work with coolants prepared for power electronics. These coolants are characterized by their low electrical conductivity under 5 μS/cm which ensures no short circuits are produced in the stack or the power electronics used to cool down.

Figure 1: FCS outline including the anode, cathode and coolant circuits

3.2 Suitability for the heavy-duty vehicle application

The E-60-HD Fuel Cell Engine was designed particularly for heavy-duty vehicle applications and for stable power generation, which is perfectly in line with the objectives of the All-In Zero project. This FC system is protected against FC stack degradation due to its relatively high idle current and the moderate dynamics it is designed for. On one hand, limiting the minimum current density implies that the FC stack does not operate at high-voltage conditions, thus avoiding the high overpotential that may cause the degradation of the catalysts. On the other hand, moderate dynamics helps the flow management on the cathode, anode, and cooling circuits and prevents asymmetries in the current density distribution on each cell and between cells. One of the main causes of degradation of PEMFC is the dynamic operation, which produces cathode/anode starvation, cell flooding, and local overheating of the cell.

Cathode or anode starvation occur when the H_2 or the O_2 in the air are consumed at a faster rate than they are supplied. This may happen under sudden increases in the power demand when the H_2 valve or the electric motor powering the compressor does not act on the flows fast enough. Therefore, decreasing the rate of change of the power demand implies that the discrepancy between the consumption and the supply is reduced.

Cell flooding may happen due to the cell design or due to water management issues. Water management is critical in FCs since it is also responsible for providing enough humidity to the membrane to decrease the ohmic losses and, thus, increase the stack efficiency. In this sense, some cells are designed to be self-humidified by accumulating water in the anode recirculation circuit, by including external humidifiers, or by designing the flow channels in such a way that water is retained up to a certain extent but avoiding flooding. Nonetheless, despite a good design in both the anode and cathode flow fields, high dynamics may regardless imply water accumulation locally. Therefore, an issue in the water management system may imply water accumulation over certain levels, thus saturating the membrane, negatively affecting proton transport, and potentially causing mechanical damage due to the humidification and drying-out cycles. In this sense, decreasing the dynamics of the FC system operation eases the water management, and coupled with the open flow field of the cells in the stack, the risk of water flooding is minimized and the expected lifetime of the stack increases.

Finally, local overheating is produced due to asymmetries in the electric current density distribution along the cell and the comparatively low reaction of the cooling circuit. Again, these asymmetries are produced mainly during highly dynamic operation, where phenomena such as membrane flooding and starvation may occur. Therefore, low-dynamic operation implies that the cooling circuit has more time to react to homogenize the temperature field in the cells while it avoids the asymmetries in the electric current density, thus minimizing the risk of local cell degradation.

Therefore, the E-60-HD Fuel Cell Engine is expected to have a long lifetime, which is one of the requisites for the FC heavy-duty vehicle application. Furthermore, this system has already been commercialized, which implies that it complies with all the requisites in terms of safety for transport applications. It includes a series of emergency response procedures in case of hydrogen leaks, fire, or collision.

3.3 Justification

The maximum power output of the E-60-HD Fuel Cell Engine is 60 kW, which may seem lower than the power required by the powertrain system of a heavy-duty vehicle. Nonetheless, this does not pose a problem in fulfilling the objectives of the All-In Zero project and the architecture and operation of this system offer a set of advantages that were decisive in selecting it:

- 1) As explained in the previous section, the FC system is fully compatible with the FC heavy-duty vehicle and decentralized power generation applications, thus offering a significant lifetime, high performance, and safety measures. The moderate dynamics of the FC system allow for reaching high durability, which minimizes the number of FC system replacements for the expected lifetime of 1000000 km for heavy-duty vehicles. This could impact positively both the environmental impact and the total cost of ownership of the integrated powertrain system.
- 2) The low power of the FC system (compared to the power required by heavy-duty vehicles) is fully compatible with the modularity trend of the FC industry. In this sense, it was expected to consider several FC systems to power the e-motor of the vehicle and a high-capacity battery pack to support and supply the additional power required during the power demand peaks. Therefore, the impact on the project outcomes is negligible since the modeling framework will only have to consider a different number of FC systems, which has already been considered in other projects by the UPV research group. Furthermore, the low dynamics of these systems make them highly compatible with the range-extender architecture that has been widely recognized as a key architecture to ensure high performance and durability, particularly for heavy-duty vehicles.
- 3) The research team from UPV acquired in the past a similar FC system and has extensive experience with the operation of this technology, its architecture, and where it can be sensorized. In this sense, one of the main technical reasons why the E-60-HD Fuel Cell Engine was selected is its packaging. The main parts of the cathode, anode, and cooling circuits are particularly accessible since there is optical access to them and some of the components can be easily modified to integrate the sensors required to obtain the information defined in deliverables 3.1 and 3.2. In contrast, there are other FC systems, such as that integrated into the Hyundai Nexu FCV (acquired by UPV) in other projects, whose packaging makes adding any sensor extremely challenging and at some parts of the cathode, anode, and cooling circuits unfeasible. Therefore, the packaging and accessibility to the main components of the E-60-HD Fuel Cell Engine were key factors determining the suitability of such an FC system to fulfill the requirements of the All-In Zero project.

Further from these technical reasons, it is important to note that the expected project budget was estimated based on the prices of 2021. In the FC industry, there have been a set of factors that had, as a consequence, the increase in the cost of FC technology. The first factor is common to all industries, and it is the increase in raw materials and resources coupled with the inflation of the economy. The second factor is particular to the FC industry and is the increase in the demand for FC power generation systems motivated by the sustainability policies implemented by the members of the European Union, which also impacted the delivery time of these products. This was confirmed by contacting several FC system suppliers, and it was found that the E-60-HD Fuel Cell Engine complied with an acceptable cost for the project, provided that some adjustments had to be made, and with the delivery time required to fulfill the project schedule. Note that the delivery time of other companies for a single FC system was 8-12 months while for the E-60-HD Fuel Cell Engine, it was 1 month.

4. Fuel cell system technical specifications

The selected FCS, a Nuvera E-60-HD Fuel Cell Engine, has the specifications shown in Table 1:

Parameter	Specifications
Gross output power	67 kW
Net output power	59 kW
Operating Voltage	175-290 VDC
Maximum operating current	375 A
Peak efficiency	58%
Dimensions (L x W x H)	1000 x 600 x 500 mm
Mass	190 kg
Ambien operating temperatures	-30° to 45°C
Coolant	De-ionized water or glycol mix
Oxidant	Air
Fuel quality	SAE J2719, ISO 14687-2
Air supply pressure	0.70 - 1.05 bar
Fuel supply pressure	12.5 - 15.0 bar
Input power for balance of plant	1.2 kW @ 27 VDC // 8.25 kW @ 375 VDC
Communication protocol	CAN 2.0B
Target lifetime	10,000 hours

Table 1 Nuvera E-60-HD Specifications.

4.1 Anode

The anode is one of the two main electrodes in a fuel cell. Its primary function is to facilitate the electrochemical oxidation of hydrogen fuel. In the specific case of our selected fuel cell, it has a passive recirculating system and a pressure regulating valve, in charge of maintaining adequate hydrogen pressure levels. The key specifications of the anode circuit can be found in Table 2.

Parameter	Specifications
Hydrogen input pressure	12.5 to 15.0 bar absolute.
Hydrogen input temperature	-30° to 45° C
Hydrogen input massflow	Up to 1.4g/s

Table 2 Anode, range of main parameters.

4.2 Cathode

The cathode circuit consists of an electric compressor that serves to control the airflow, thereby adjusting the cathode stoichiometry based on the fuel cell (FC) current density. Sequentially after the electric compressor, there is a heat exchanger that is supplied with coolant from the primary cooling circuit. This coolant helps to reduce the inlet temperature of the cathode in the fuel cell stack. The pressure within this circuit is managed through the manipulation of pressure losses occurring within both the stack and the heat exchanger. The environmental conditions under which the FCS can be operated can be found in Table 3.

Parameter	Specifications
Air input pressure	0.7 to 1.05 bar absolute.
Air input temperature	-30° to 45° C
Air input massflow	Up to 70 g/s

Table 3 Cathode, range of acceptable environmental conditions.

4.3 Cooling circuit

From the side of the fuel cell, the cooling system (Table 4) is composed of the inlet and outlet of the coolant circuit, a coolant pump, a thermostatic valve, and a warm-up resistance for cold start conditions. On the facility side, a heat exchanger system, a deionization filter, and an expansion volume with a pressure relief valve. Is important to note that the thermal module must maintain electrical isolation of coolant, and the impedance of the equipotential bonding between components must prevent a difference in voltage potential.

Parameter	Specifications
Coolant input pressure requirements	0.0 to 0.55 bar gauge
Coolant input flow	Up to 150 liter/min
Maximum heat rejection	75.2 kW
Fuel cell coolant volume	10 liters

Table 4 Cooling circuit, range of main parameters.

4.4 Interfaces

One of the most important aspects to consider when integrating the Fuel Cell into the testing facility is its interface. In Figure 2 and Figure 3, provided by the Fuel Cell supplier, it is possible to see all of them.

Figure 2 Fuel Cell Interfaces.

All these interfaces will be covered by the different systems on the testing facilities as it is explained on section 6 of this document.

Figure 3 Fuel Cell Interfaces location.

5. Sensorization

5.1 General

In Figure 4, a schematic of the FC system installed in the bench can be seen, in green, the variables that can be obtained directly from sensors already installed in the bench or in the FC are shown. Those variables will be retrieved via CAN communication by the test bed automation system, AVL PUMA. In orange, additional variables that will be instrumented are shown, and in red those variables that would have been desirable but for which no way of instrumenting could be found.

Figure 4 FC Schematic with proposed sensorization

5.2 Anode

For the anode circuit, it would have been desirable to instrument, both its pressure and temperature. Because of constructive constraints of the fuel cell system, the tube in which the sensors need to be placed is made from a very rigid plastic material that cannot be perforated, ensuring no cracks will happen, as can be seen in Figure 5, those variables will not be instrumented.

Figure 5 - Anode side of the system

5.3 Cathode

From the cathode side, temperatures, pressures, and relative humidity, after the compressor and after the heat exchanger will be measured. For these type K thermocouples, piezoresistive pressure sensors, and hygrometric relative humidity sensors will be used. In the exhaust side of the cathode, the pressure and temperature will be as well measured.

5.4 Cooling circuit

From the cooling circuit perspective, the only sensors that could be added are a mass flow meter for the coolant fluid, together with thermocouples to monitor the temperature of the inlet and outlet flows of the heat exchanger interface to correctly monitor the energy flows. The mass flow meter for the coolant is optional and its measurement will depend on the compatibility with the coolant.

6. Test bench integration

6.1 Test bench requirements

The Nuvera E-60-HD is a complete FCS which is composed of an FC stack and its BoP. However, to be able to test its performance under different conditions, some additional technical requirements need to be considered.

The E-60-HD has its own cooling system that is used to cool down the FC stack and make sure it complies with the temperature limits in which the FC can be operated safely (under 80°C). However, due to the electrical properties of the system, not any kind of coolant would be appropriate for the FC. In a diesel engine, the electric conductivity of the coolant is not significant because the produced energy comes from a combustion process (thermal energy) and is transformed into mechanical energy to move the vehicle. Nevertheless, the produced energy in an FC comes from an induced current produced by the movement of electrons in the electrochemical reactions that take place in the stack. Thus, having a fluid with a high conductivity near the stack could disturb the energy generation process or even damage the stack properties and worsen its performance.

Figure 6 Electrical conductivity of different coolants.

The special coolant used in the FCS is Glystantin FC G 20-00/50, which is composed of 48% of ethylene glycol and distilled water. The advantage of glystantin respect to other glycol mixes is its long-term protection against conductivity increments, as it can be noted in Figure 6.

The cooling system integrated in the BoP of the E-60-HD can be used to keep the temperature of the stack inside its operational limits. For this purpose, the cooling system has been connected to a heat exchanger that controls the temperature of the fluid that goes in and out of the system. The hot glystantin that goes out of the FC can be cooled down by exchanging heat with cold glycol. The amount of cold fluid used is controlled by the opening of a valve which considers the required FC operating temperature, depending on the required temperature the valve lets a higher or lower amount of cold glycol in or out of the system. The cold temperature of the glycol is kept by using the ConsysCool 200.

The AVL ConsysCool 200, shown in Figure 7, is the coolant conditioning system used in the facility. This technology is composed of two circuits: primary and secondary. The primary circuit connects the ConsysCool with the unit under test (UUT). In this case, the primary circuit is not directly connected to the UUT, as it has already been mentioned, but to a heat exchanger. The ConsysCool and the cooling system of the E-60-HD both include a pump and the use of both at the same time would not allow the fluid to be controlled properly. Thus, the heat exchanger allows proper and easier temperature control. Therefore, the ConsysCool primary circuit uses glycol and the secondary uses water coming from the network of the building.

Figure 7 ConsysCool 200.

The E-60-HD uses H₂ and air to produce electricity. The H₂ needed for this purpose needs to be high purity H₂, more than 99.999% pure. The fulfillment of this special requirement has been achieved by the acquisition of a H₂ generation facility (Figure 8). This device can generate up to 0.71 kg H₂/hr and the whole facility includes a number of tanks that can store a maximum of 130 kg of H₂ at 330 bar.

Figure 8 Hydrogen generation facility.

The amount of H₂ generated is enough for the E-60-HD. However, to obtain the required 99.999% purity, the tanks had to go through a purging process. This process consisted of refilling the tanks several times to eliminate other gases that could have gone into the tanks while they were empty. A gas analyzer was used to test the quality of the obtained gas.

The fuel pressure that goes inside the FCS needs to be controlled so that it is not above or below the operating FC limits. This value is regulated by the AVL HyTron (Hydrogen Supply and Consumption Measurement System), shown in Figure 9. In this system, H₂ is at 25 bar at the inlet and between 12.5 and 14 bar at the outlet. This device is used to control the pressure, but it is also used to purge the H₂ inlet by using N₂ and control the amount of fuel that goes into the system.

Moreover, not all the amount of fuel that goes into the FCS is consumed. The quantity of H₂ that is not used is purged by the FCS by the opening of a valve. This exhausted H₂ goes out through the cathode, and it is absorbed by an air extractor that frees it to the ambient.

Figure 9 HyTron integrated in the system.

On the cathode side, the air conditioning on the inlet do not need to be controlled. However, this control would be a specific requirement for the type of tests that will be performed during the proposed experimental campaign. Air temperature and humidity are parameters that could influence the performance of the FC and thus need to be studied. To achieve this control, the AVL AirTake 1500, shown in Figure 10, is used. This equipment allows a temperature control from 15°C to 40°C and a relative humidity range from 20% to 80%. This device uses a resistance to heat the air that goes into the system. Besides, to cool down the air, a heat exchanger uses cold water coming from an external chiller. The used chiller is able to cool water up to 5°C to avoid freezing issues. For now, the AT1500 can increase humidity up to 80% by adding air vapor coming from a vaporizer. However, as this device does not dry air, to obtain low RH values the test would be dependent on the weather conditions.

Figure 10 AirTake 1500.

Finally, to simulate the electrical behavior of a vehicle, the Puma system and FCS need to be connected to a battery emulator that produces the required power or current demand. The used battery emulator is the AVL E-Storage BTE 250 (Figure 11), which can work up to 250 kW. The power that can be generated by this device is much higher than the required one, but it would be necessary if the testbed was used to test higher power FCS and it would be an appropriate value for a FCHDV.

Figure 11 E-Storage BTE250.

6.2 Fuel cell/test bench adaptation

The cooling of the system to keep the temperature of the stack under control depends on the temperature of the coolant, the PID temperature and the use of a heat exchanger. The heat exchanger used to decrease the glysantin temperature is a plate heat exchanger model S14A-ST. This system has a dissipation power of 114 kW for a temperature difference of 5 degrees Celsius. Thus, it is oversized for an FC of 60 kW as the E-60-HD in which the usual temperature gap is around 25 degrees Celsius. However, the used testbed was designed to fit up to 200 kW FCS, which would require a powerful heat exchanger as the installed one, which can be seen in Figure 12.

Figure 12 Testbed heat exchanger S14A-ST.

Glysantin is a low-conductivity coolant, which is appropriate for use in PEMFC. However, this fluid is quite corrosive and its use can generate particles in the cooling system that may increase its conductivity. The FCS is limited to operate under a conductivity not higher than 15 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. Thus, to keep this value stable a particle filter has been added to the testbed. The used filters have the particularity of working under high temperatures. The chosen model for these conditions is the Spectrapure MaxTemp DI™ de-ionizing cartridge from SpectraPure (Figure 13), which is able to stand temperatures up to 80°C.

Figure 13 Spectrapure MaxTemp DI™ connected to the cooling system.

The FCS already has a sensor that measures the conductivity of the coolant. Nevertheless, due to the importance of this value for the proper performance of the system, a new sensor has been included in the testbed. The chosen sensor is the Burket Type 8222 presented in Figure 14, which is able to measure between $0.05 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and $10 \text{ mS}/\text{cm}$. The high precision of this sensor allows to make conductivity studies to understand the influence of this parameter on the performance of the system.

Figure 14 Burket Type 8222 installed on the testbed.

In the cathode outlet, a significant amount of water is generated. Part of this water is in a liquid state, and it is removed from the system by using a floating valve, which deviates this water from the system to the water network. In addition, some water vapor is also generated, and it can be reused. The water vapor goes through the aftercooler shown in Figure 15, which condensates it to a liquid phase so that it can easily be added to the building water network.

Figure 15 Aftercooler used in the system.

Finally, the testbed activities also require some operating procedures. To ensure the FCS reaches a steady state in a fast way, the stack needs to be close to its operating temperature (around 65°C). Thus, a warm-up procedure has been designed to increase the temperature of the stack in a soft way. At the beginning of the warm-up, the stack is usually quite cold, the first step is larger than the rest to give it time to reach the desired temperature. The warm-up procedure ends at the highest current so that the polarization curve tests can start right after it. The used procedure is shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16 Designed warm-up procedure for the start-up phase.

Finally, after any test, the FCS stays in idle for a minimum of 60 seconds so that the shutdown of the FCS is done from the minimum current and is less aggressive.

6.3 Feasible testing activities

The present testbed will be used to perform different experimental activities that can provide useful data in the current FCV context. The owned facility has been prepared to produce valuable sets of data in different operating scenarios.

Firstly, the FCS needs to be characterized in steady-state conditions to understand how different air conditions can influence the performance of the system. For this purpose, as the polarization curve represents the best way to measure the performance of an FC, some polarization curves will be carried out under different air temperatures and relative humidity levels. To simulate a steady-state performance, some tests were done to detect how long it takes the FCS to reach a stable state. After some 10, 5, 3 and 1 minute tests, it was decided that a 3-minute step stabilization polarization curve would be enough to reach a steady performance at each current step. In addition, 15 different points were selected to obtain a good approximation of the polarization curve shape, which can be seen in Figure 17.

These tests will be carried out under different air conditions that represent different and feasible weather conditions. The chosen conditions range from 15°C to 40°C and from 20% to 80% of relative humidity. Due to the variability in the established conditions, the temperature will be changed in 5°C steps and the relative humidity in ~20% steps.

Figure 17 Steps of the chosen polarization curves.

After the steady characterization, as it was explained in detail in the previous deliverables concerning the experimental methodology, some dynamic tests will be carried out to understand how different levels of dynamics can influence the performance of the system (Figure 18). The current limits of the operation, as well as the dynamic restrictions, have been chosen considering the specifications of the Nuvera E-60-HD.

Figure 18 Dynamic characterization test.

Finally, as the E-60-HD FCS is an appropriate system for modular use in a HD FCV, a typical HD driving cycle will be modelled in a simulation platform under the performance restrictions of this FCS (dynamics and power). The simulations will provide the driving conditions profile to test it in the facility. An example of these testing activities is shown in Figure 19. These tests will allow to understand the impact of different dynamics or operating conditions that could influence real driving.

Figure 19 Driving profiles under different dynamics in a similar FCS (Nuvera E-60-HD).